

**INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY
FUTURE**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6481925>

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the concept of innovation, the problems of innovative development of regional economies, the process of innovative development, the structure of innovation, statistics of the innovation process in the Bukhara region.*

Key words: *Innovation, innovation activity, investment, product innovation, technological innovation, marketing innovation, organizational innovation, innovation value.*

Humans are afraid of everything new. To a greater extent, this manifests itself in the transition period, especially in periods of crisis, when there is socio-psychological instability, and the introduction of a new one is perceived as a threat to the existing situation.

According to the latest statistics, large enterprises with more than 1,000 employees are the most active in innovation.

This can be explained by the fact that large enterprises have large financial, industrial, human and political resources - the ability to defend their interests, which largely determines success in the competitive struggle. The experience of foreign companies also shows that innovative development is more favorable for large enterprises and corporations.

Innovative activity is an activity aimed at finding and implementing innovations in order to expand the range and improve product quality, improve technology and organize production.

For the development of the economy and social sphere of the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-March 2021, 35,6 trillion soums of investments in fixed assets were spent from all sources of financing. In dollar terms, they

amounted to 3,4 billion US dollars, and the growth rate in comparable prices to the corresponding period of 2020 was recorded at the level of 96,5%.¹

The main condition for the innovative activity of an enterprise is to take into account all morally obsolete, obsolete resources lagging behind the development path, as well as errors, failures and miscalculations. Innovative ideas can come from external and internal sources.

Innovation is the creation or improvement of a product (product, work, service) in a new form, the introduction or improvement of a new form of production process, the introduction of new marketing or organizational methods of doing business, the creation of jobs or the external end result of innovative activity, which includes the establishment relations.

According to our study on the example of the Bukhara region, in 2019, 172 enterprises and organizations independently produced innovative products, works and services. Of these, 168 are small businesses and micro-firms².

Table 1

Innovative products developed in the Bukhara region

Indicators	2019, %
In 2019, it was mastered for the first time	40,1
Improved in 2017-2019	21,4
Mastered for the first time in 2017-2018.	38,5

Table 2

Innovative products of own production,

¹ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/4.Investments%20and%20construction-2.pdf

² Innovatsiya_2019_uz

volume of works, services (excluding VAT and excise duty) (million soums)

Indicators	2019 y,
In 2019, it was mastered for the first time	67206,9
Improved in 2017-2019	137563,1
Mastered for the first time in 2017-2018.	39439,0

Table 3

Technological, marketing and organizational innovation spending in 2019 by funding source and region

Indicators	2019, %
Organization's own funds	6,3
Foreign investment	85,4
Commercial bank loans	8,3

In January-March 2021, at the expense of the own funds of enterprises and organizations, 10 131,1 billion soums of investments in fixed assets, or 28.4% of their total volume, were disbursed. At the expense of the population, 4 595,5 billion soums of investments were disbursed, or 12,9%. Due to direct foreign investments, 4 243,1 billion soums were spent, which, compared to the same period in 2020, is more by 1,0 percentage points, or 11,9% of their total volume³.

³ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/4.Investments%20and%20construction-2.pdf

According to the statistics of enterprises and organizations that introduced innovations in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019, the largest share of innovations by type of economic activity is observed in the manufacturing industry, which is 51,9%.

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